

DeRadicalisation
in Europe and Beyond: Detect, Resolve, Reintegrate

D.6.5

Artificial Intelligence, Human Rights and civil liberties

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List of Abbreviations

AI- Artificial Intelligence, computer systems that can function like the human mind

ARCGU- Anti-Racism Coordination Governmental Unit

Big Data- a database of various types and in diverse formats that come from multiple sources

GDPR- The General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons concerning the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (OJ L 119, 4.5.2016).

GPAI- Global Partnership for Artificial Intelligence

IAIC- Israeli Artificial Intelligence Committee

INCD- Israel National Cyber Directorate

Machine Learning- a set of methods designed to perform cognitive tasks by computers

Online/offline- cases in which the physical and virtual space depend on one another

SACU- Israel's State Attorney Cyber Unit

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About the Project

D.Rad is a comparative study of radicalisation and polarisation in Europe and beyond. It aims to identify the actors, networks, and wider social contexts driving radicalisation, particularly among young people in urban and peri-urban areas. D.Rad conceptualises this through the I-GAP spectrum (injustice-grievance-alienation-polarisation), with the goal of moving towards measurable evaluations of deradicalisation programmes. Our intention is to identify the building blocks of radicalisation, which include a sense of being victimised; a sense of being thwarted or lacking agency in established legal and political structures; and coming under the influence of "us vs them" formulations of identity.

D.Rad benefits from an exceptional breadth of backgrounds. The project spans national contexts, including the UK, France, Italy, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Finland, Slovenia, Bosnia, Serbia, Kosovo, Israel, Iraq, Turkey, Georgia, Austria, and several minority nations. It bridges academic disciplines ranging from political science and cultural studies to social psychology and artificial intelligence. Dissemination methods include D.Rad labs, D.Rad hubs, policy papers, academic workshops, visual outputs and digital galleries. As such, D.Rad establishes a rigorous foundation to test practical interventions geared to prevention, inclusion and deradicalisation.

With the possibility of capturing the trajectories of seventeen nations and several minority nations, the project will provide a unique evidence base for the comparative analysis of law and policy as nation-states adapt to new security challenges. The process of mapping this variety and its links to national contexts will be crucial in uncovering strengths and weaknesses in existing interventions. Furthermore, D.Rad accounts for the problem that processes of radicalisation often occur in circumstances that escape the control and scrutiny of traditional national frameworks of justice. The participation of AI professionals in modelling, analysing and devising solutions to online radicalisation will be central to the project's aims.

Executive Summary/Abstract

The democratic framework rests upon the people's (demos) sovereignty. It relies on majority-based political representation and fundamental human rights, which vary from country to country according to the socio-political circumstances and cultural context. This report offers an empirical overview of the theoretical and practical tension between developing human-like artificial intelligence (AI) technologies for social and security purposes and preserving human freedoms and rights through law. This tension has risen parallel to the sovereign state's desire to maintain collective and individual safety among citizens while exploiting digital tools (specifically in social networks). It focuses on two main concepts emerging from the extensive development of AI technologies: discrimination and bias, inevitably resulting in inequality. In coherence with the D.Rad framework of radicalisation as a process, social exclusion that derives from inequality might pose a potential risk in leading to broader notions and feelings of *Injustice* and *Grievance*, developing and creating linkage to *Alienation*, resulting in *Polarisation* (The I-GAP spectrum). In some cases, AI machinery can assist governments in keeping citizens safe from online radicalisation, which may lead to violence. Still, in many other cases, the capability to develop suitable non-biased AI solutions directed against online radicalisation can only be accomplished in the aftermath, examining online users who posted online documentation of offline violent acts.

After a short introduction (1), Section 2 offers background on legal and constitutional issues concerning the use of human-like technology for everyday social, economic and political needs (e.g. related to job interviews, health systems, or expediting various legal procedures). It highlights the challenges that arise from using the "automatic" design and operation of artificial intelligence, which might promote, consciously or not, discriminatory practices (2.1). The following sub-sections (2.2; 2.3) discuss the issue of techniques aimed at applying non-discrimination within the development of advanced AI systems, including steps in which developers can devise procedures for equality and inclusion.

Section 3 offers some reflections concerning attempts to design "neutral" machines that might result in an internal bias towards minorities based on the normative assumptions of the socio-political system and their definition of "objectivity" in representation. It might lead to the exclusion of other groups by replicating biases due to the use of narrow lexical components within AI designs.

Section 4 discusses the tension between legislation and security-oriented actions in cyberspace (as well as the difference between security and civil defence) and initiatives that seek to preserve fundamental freedoms as a part of human rights, which may conflict. Next, it presents some insights from the Israeli case, as an example of the connection between "offline" practices and "online" characteristics, and the ways of bypassing state laws and utilising social media to perform acts of extremism, which has the effect of increasing existing tensions followed by racism, xenophobia and nationalism (4.1). Digital platforms have enabled the emergence of three main threats: incitement, fake news and the copycat syndrome, sometimes aided by digital bots. The three reflect how online inspiration can lead to offline actualisation.

This section addresses the need to keep civilians' online activities safe from harm by relying on their ability to use cyberspace anonymously, and the institutional actions undertaken by the state (4.2) with the aim of finding some accountability for those who violate the freedoms

of these spaces. Further, it considers the additional perspective of non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and their transformation through social media, which has expanded their ability to promote deradicalisation through activities designed to safeguard human rights (4.3). It highlights that civil society can play a crucial role in receiving and containing data regarding undetected discrimination and biased attitudes that the state has trouble locating.

Section 5 offers concluding remarks concerning the relationship between offline acts and online activities that tend to radicalise other users, initially experiencing feelings of exclusion. by exposing them to violent content, hence further reflecting on the I-GAP spectrum components.. First, one must consider the challenges posed by discriminatory and biased elements that may result while building an artificial intelligence mechanism – also regarding machine learning and training processes – and especially a textual framework for algorithmic design. Beyond that, cooperation between state security institutions and civil society (which is directly connected to the public) can direct attention to existing AI state systems that express discriminations, as reported by volunteers and the people, by creating shared datasets of reports. In this way, through broad transparency, it is possible to lead to an unbiased approach among official institutions which will also permeate unofficial institutions among civil society and the private sector. Receiving and sharing ad hoc data from NGOs and GOs can assist the goal of helping eliminate "automatic-made" violations of human rights, such as those on discriminatory AI systems which exist "unawarely" but still needs to be attended, thus avoiding the duplication of discriminatory discourse that may someday be perceived as "natural".

1. Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) does not have a single definition. The common assumption is that it refers to computer systems that can function similarly to the human mind, considering that both cannot become identical. AI can include a variety of techniques that have grown out of it, such as heuristic search, game playing, expert systems, data mining, etc. The AI field has various subdomains that have been formed within it, like reasoning, planning vision, natural language processing, robotics, and teaching machine self-learning skills (Wang, 2019, 7-8). Among other things, AI is deployed in situations involving large amounts of data that are required to be analysed rapidly. "Big Data" is a term used to describe databases of various types and in diverse formats that come from multiple sources (Hebrew Linguistic Academy, 2022). It is a field of information that can assist in fields that involve primary consideration of civic needs (i.e., security, public health, financials, etc.) (The Israel Academy for Science and Humanities, 2022). "Machine Learning" is a set of methods used to perform cognitive tasks, and describes the ability of the system to learn from examples and apply the knowledge to new information (Even and Siman Tov, 2020, p.29).

By virtue of its mechanical and scientific background, AI has been involved in several fields of knowledge and activities: from job applications and recruitment to automated judicial systems, AI can offer the best solutions to be rapidly applied to manage sensitive data. Its functioning and processes have also been deemed objective and neutral, as machines "cannot do wrong". However, in 2015, it was revealed, for instance and among other cases, that Amazon uses AI tools to map out employees' resumes and *discriminates* against women (Wachter et al. 2021). In 2016 the issue of *biased bots* preoccupied many in the western world who saw a replication of problems of online racism and sexism. It meant that machine learning risks incorrectly identifying similarities, thus inadvertently offending users, something that engineers need to take into account according to scholars in the field. It revealed that AI has trouble differentiating reasons from actions, since it works automatically and is designed by people (Kabir 2016). Inspections in 2019 also found that an algorithm used for treating patients considered their race in some health systems (Wachter et al. 2021). This strengthens the concern that segregative perceptions are commodities that people might implement in AI systems. The European Union has been vigorously active in digital market regulations in the past few years, considering AI's influence on job recruitment and new occupations to follow. In 2020, the European Commission presented the reform of a white paper to ensure access and use of artificial intelligence guided through a human-centred ethical approach. Also, the white paper focuses on the services of public interest as a crucial point, both in the dimension of granting citizens' security, at the same time safeguarding their fundamental freedoms and rights. Second, the impact of AI should be assessed not only in an individual dimension, but vis-à-vis society as whole, in order to "enable a trustworthy and secure development of AI" (p. 2). The relevance of the protection of fundamental rights at stake is also testified by the recommendations framed by the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA) in a dedicated 2020 study, specifically addressing a fundamental rights-oriented approach in dealing with artificial intelligence. ¹

Following this, the Commission issued 2021 a proposal for a series of laws regarding artificial intelligence and its integration within the existing legislative frameworks of the

¹ "Getting the future right. Artificial Intelligence and fundamental rights", FRA, 2020, available at <https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2020/artificial-intelligence-and-fundamental-rights>.

European Union, with a view to the global use of artificial intelligence (Justo-Hanani, 2022, 137-138).

In view of its actual utility in simultaneously processing vast amounts of data using methods beyond human capability, ideas about infallibility, "omniscience", and trustworthiness of AI have progressively developed. However, such a characterisation may not always be accurate, since it has long been observed that AI-driven decision-making processes are subject to biases. This means that, notwithstanding the fact that automated choices are faster and "science-based", the human input and contribution to AI learning processes are relevant and sometimes decisive. In this regard, it is apparent how AI can affect individuals and groups, their choices, and their lives. At the same time, AI is dependent on a specific previous data set, which may well reflect a discriminatory selection, leading AI to cause discrimination as an "automatic" result.

The sources of discrimination were not born with AI technologies, but every system has received parameters from its designers which rely on patterns of behaviour drawn from online users (Rimer, 2020). Naturally, this impacts fundamental rights, directly or indirectly, jeopardising, for instance, the principles of equality and equal treatment as a result of illegitimate differentiations among people and a fortiori among social groups. As will be highlighted in this report, stereotypes and prejudices present in offline public spaces may well be replicated – and further enforced – in the (often private) online context. They may concern, among other things, personal or subjective qualities, such as gender, ethnicity, race, religion, political opinions or socio-economic conditions. The alleged neutrality of AI is thus increasingly challenged and questioned. A solution might be reached by combining an interdisciplinary approach involving specialists and consultants from relevant fields to improve the tool of machine learning (Sokolov 2022).

This report offers an assessment of the role of AI in tackling and responding to radicalisation, taking into account several factors. Section 2 will review central theoretical legal issues concerning AI implementation within a constitutional framework and address the "clash" between technologies and fundamental rights and liberties. Section 3 will discuss the role of AI in detecting radicalisation and how it may lead to discrimination, especially regarding the over-representation of some groups and under-detection of others, as well as exploring how bias may prevent deradicalisation initiatives. Section 4 will focus on AI and state security and assess the interplays between the physical "public" and the virtual "cyber" spaces in relation to the notion of deradicalisation. In this regard, the analysis will also consider the influence of the digital space (particularly social media platforms) vis-à-vis civil society and human rights and the connection between offline activities and online communication. Finally, Section 5 will draw some conclusive remarks on the overall topic.

2. AI and legal issues

Law and STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) are constantly and progressively in dialogue. Law itself and law drafting processes are increasingly affected by the advancement of science, which has opened new ethical frontiers and brought innovative accomplishments, putting pressure on lawmakers and legal scholars to keep up with dynamic scenarios. As technology advances, various dilemmas and questions are posed by biolaw and bioethics, as well as research involving the study of hybrid human-machine systems and entities. This does not entail a stark choice between preserving the legal status quo and

embracing new scientific challenges. Rather, it requires seeking a careful balance when addressing the issues and fundamental principles at stake.

AI's relevance comes into this picture, even though it is not an unknown or new phenomenon, due to the prominent role played by computers (and computational sciences) in everyday life, along with the expansion of the virtual and online space in all human activities. Moreover, the most heated debates concern the automatising of human actions, meaning to what extent and within which boundaries this may occur. In this regard, questions have arisen in fields where human cognitive processes are primarily involved, namely in the case of sensitive topics and moral issues involving human reasoning, which cannot be replaced by artificial intelligence mechanics. One can recall criminal judicial decisions, where personal liberty can be restricted, as well as the case of automated selection in job applications, where equal opportunities may be jeopardised by unfair treatment and discrimination towards gender, racial, religious and ethnic minorities. This may happen, for instance, because of prejudices, stereotypes and institutional racism, which may well be reflected by and incorporated into machines. Indeed, the latter are not self-sufficient "entities"; machines may well suffer from the very same limits (and biases) affecting human behaviour, since they (still) rely upon human interventions (and data set) in order to function and learn.

2.1 AI and constitutional aspects

Several issues and challenges come into the picture also as far as constitutional topics are involved in the use of AI. From a private law point of view, scholarship has explicitly focused on liability issues related to the operation of machines where illicit actions have been committed. In the public law domain, as Casonato (2019) suggests, (at least) four macro topics are involved. He highlights the relevance of privacy in the management of (frequently sensitive) Big Data, monopolistic risks, implications for democracy, and respect for the principle of equality. Accordingly, it is not a coincidence that algorithms in themselves have been deemed inherently "unconstitutional" (Simoncini, 2019).

Managing data on a mass scale enables more and more accuracy and efficiency in the profiling of identities and individual habits (Casonato, 2019, p. 106). It means that even though we make decisions and show preferences according to individual needs, desires and "ideals", our choices are not as free as one may suppose.² The constant data flow regarding consumers' routines and patterns usually extends beyond the scope of "monitoring" social behaviours and enables them to be predicted with high precision. Our privacy is the core issue when it comes to the use of advanced technologies in everyday life. However, we are limited in our actual ability to "accept" or "reject" the exploitation of our personal data by the mentioned technological process. In this context, informed consent has been playing a crucial balancing role between the fast progression of science and technology and the simultaneous need to safeguard a 'fair' use of (often sensitive) personal data³. As has been argued, however, our consent to actually (and actively) participate in the overall processing of personal data and their exploitation – for instance, commercial choices or exchanging individual personal informations – is becoming *willfully and consciously misinformed*. Casonato thoroughly

² On profiling, see also: Hildebrandt, 2008.

³ For instance, as stated in the White Paper: "By analysing large amounts of data and identifying links among them, AI may also be used to retrace and de-anonymise data about persons, creating new personal data protection risks even in respect to datasets that per se do not include personal data", p. 11.

explains that "the legal category of informed consent has become a mere *fiction* which exposes us daily to profiling in all our dimensions and activities" (Ibid, p. 107).

A further challenge emerges if one focuses on the new dimensions of non-traditional "powers" handling and processing *those* personal data. Privately owned companies and organisations which use sensitive data often operate through economic dynamics, in a transnational framework and beyond the national rules of each legal system (Sassi, 2018). If we look at social media platforms, it becomes even more evident that these processes *cannot* be neutral. In fact, "being owned by a few wealthy commercial companies, [social media platforms] pursue profit through the collection, processing and sale of users' personal data, which are then exploited to "profile" them", i.e., predict their behaviour (Simoncini and Suweis, 2019, p.94). These platforms "enable individual and collective behaviour to be influenced as well" (Ibid).⁴

In EU law, the legal framework of the right to privacy and the protection of personal data is mainly represented by the GDPR; the concept of discrimination is also linked to the processing of data itself (Berendt, 2022, p.4). As has been effectively underlined by Simoncini and Suweis, three principles in the GDPR inform and define the algorithmic decision-making framework: transparency, non-exclusivity, and non-discrimination (2019, p. 98). Under Articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR, as Simoncini explains, the first refers to a person's right to know if he or she is the addressee of automated decision processes, as well as that person's entitlement to ask for further information about the reason for a decision. It is connected to the right of anyone who is an addressee of a decision to be assured that the latter will not be solely based on an automated process, and the right, accordingly, to obtain human intervention and control, as per Article 22 of the GDPR (Simoncini and Suweis, 2019, p. 98-99). The meaning of the third principle is relatively straightforward in its formulation.

The concept of an abstract "marketplace of ideas" might lead one to think that a sort of "automatic" (human) selection of *good* opinions and viewpoints would have naturally fostered a conscious, balanced and (sufficiently) pluralist society. As a result, there would be no room for an "external" control over the very same ideas, since the *best* among them would have circulated in a democratic environment under the guarantee of freedom of speech. However, this may not be the case in *bubble democracies*, in which only "the best" solutions and opinions are offered to people, groups and online communities according to their values and ideals, there being no real chance to choose them on an equal basis with others (Palano, 2020). To put it differently, the marketplace of ideas is not that free if "users" cannot genuinely participate and if pluralism is restricted by choices made by algorithms on their behalf. It represents a further critical implication for the use of AI in (a virtual) social framework since people "also as citizens, are confined within increasingly closed and self-referential social media systems, which lead them to consider their own ideas as the only reasonable ones, precluding a real, plural exchange among different positions and, ultimately, fostering a social

⁴ Also in this regard, The White Paper stresses the need to build an "ecosystem of trust as a policy goal in itself". This tries to respond to citizens' concerns being left 'powerless' due to information asymmetries, especially in decision-making processes involving AI (p. 3, p. 9). Additionally, a whole section (III) is devoted to the issue, called "Ensure that AI works for people and is a force for good in society" in the 2021 Annex to the "Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Fostering a European approach to Artificial Intelligence". In particular, Par. 9 deals with "Develop a policy framework to ensure trust in AI systems".

and political regression driven by fragmentation, polarisation and radicalisation" (Casonato, 2019, p. 111).⁵

Ultimately, algorithms may challenge the principle of and the right to self-identification as reflecting individuals' self-determination. Data exploitation for profiling purposes also threatens individuals' right "to decide whether or not to belong to a group according to a construction of the negative and positive dimension" (Nardocci, 2021, p. 40). It is relatively intuitive to understand that the principle of equality risks being undermined, given the capability of AI to jeopardise equal substantive participation in the overall process, also bearing in mind the above-mentioned dynamics. Concepts such as bias, discrimination and fairness are involved: these will be addressed in the following sections.

2.2 (Anti-)discrimination: which lesson has been learnt so far?

Machines were meant to be restrained as mere "tools" and "means" for human actions but have progressively gained *agency* on their own (Simoncini, 2019). The idea that AI acts in a fully neutral way may be disproved by its very ontological nature, as its aim is to make *distinctions* between selected data (Nardocci, 2021, pp. 12-14). Thus, *how* AI distinguishes among different situations, *against* who and on *what* basis is the urgent question to be addressed, rather than *whether* it can discriminate due to its *epistemic opacity*. That is, with any automated decision-making process it is challenging to determine which parameters were used, how data were gathered and how the overall process affected the results or outputs; epistemic opacity in addition may also "intensify issues of discrimination" (Heinrichs, 2022, p.150). Some AI functions are *contingently* opaque, for example where trade secrets or know-how are involved; others are "essentially opaque" because of the machine or model complexity per se (Ibid, p. 153). However, it should be noted that AI does not always entail the same risks, and sometimes it does not pose risks.⁶

Discrimination is considered the most recurrent side effect of AI functioning (Berendt, 2022). As is well known, discrimination can be direct or indirect. In the former case, discrimination is the main actual intent underlying behaviours or actions (or omissions), where the aim is to treat individuals or groups differently due to specific characteristics, identities or belongings. Thus, the unfair, illegitimate and non-justifiable application of a differentiated treatment appears *deliberate*.⁷ Indirect forms of discrimination, on the other hand, *reflect* unequal attitudes towards individuals or groups as a side effect of behaviours or actions (or omissions) that were not intended to be illegitimate in the first place.⁸ In automated decisions, these categories become more blurred ((Hildebrandt, 2021, p. 361), confirming the *singularity* hypothesis. The latter refers to the peculiarities of algorithmic discrimination, which often transcend general and traditional concepts of anti-discrimination law (Nardocci, 2021, p. 55).

In this regard, the *training moment* is crucial in the "timeline" of AI functioning. As Nardocci (2021) underlines, the threats inherent in this phase are at least twofold. The first "occurs in

⁵ See also: Naqvi et al., 2021, pp. 838-854.

⁶ "An AI system of a chess computer does not bring the same risks as an AI system for predictive policing", F. Zuiderveen Borgesius, 2018. "Discrimination, artificial intelligence, and algorithmic Decision-making." *Linea, Council of Europe*, p. 37.

⁷ More specifically, it implies "a deliberate attempt to exclude persons from what they deserve, desire or need, if such an attempt is based on intended disrespect or a pronounced lack of concern for those persons", M. Hildebrandt, 2021. "Discrimination, Data-driven AI Systems and Practical Reason", *European Data Protection Law Review*, vol. 7, no. 3, p. 359).

⁸ Namely: "treating people differently in a way that results in the exclusion of persons due to their religion, political opinion, gender or ethnic background, even though there was no intent", *Ibidem*.

the presence of data that is not equally representative of the individual and collective components of society: the machine will work starting from an erroneous representation of reality, reproducing patterns that will produce proportionally worse effects to the detriment of the under- or over-represented category". The second refers to cases in which the machine extends the model imbued with the original prejudice, replicating it in relation to "other" cases. It should be noted, however, that in addition to the initial prejudice, the machine may also add further ones by itself (pp. 18-19). In such a case, the results provided by machines can also "worsen inequality" beyond real life asymmetries, since they are able to "influence people's ideas" as well.

Discrimination is usually neither static nor monolithic, but it may well be multidimensional, involving different aspects and qualities of individual identity (Wachter et al. 2021, p.9). Being part of a discriminated group often means belonging to a disadvantaged category, becoming the target of a social and an automated bias at the same time. In fact, sources of discrimination and unfair and unequal treatment can be multiple, due to the intersection among different factors or "protected" characteristics, such as race, gender, ethnicity, etc. Thus, awareness about the "potential of digital discrimination to reinforce existing social inequalities" should be strengthened "when multiple identities and experiences of exclusion and subordination start interacting" (Ferrer et al. 2021, p. 78).

However, at present the most significant shortcomings are due to reliance on general concepts that do not fully take account of the specificities involved in AI functioning. As Berendt (2022) has shown, this translates into two limitations: first, the traditional anti-discrimination legal apparatus provides an insufficient framework of reference⁹; second, 'transparency' and the 'right to know' (Nardocci, 2021, p.53) cannot be considered as a panacea or a sort of *carte blanche*, capable of countering the biased (thus discriminatory) mechanism through which AI can operate (and learn). This means that the different circumstances which can arise from algorithmic discrimination may not be adequately addressed and that reliance on anti-discrimination laws may not be enough, also bearing in mind that the very concept of discrimination evolves according to times and places (Berendt, 2022, p.13). In addition, categories can play a valuable role in "tracing" discrimination – and effectively confronting it – but at the same time, their crystallisation is not *that* useful. In fact, as has been argued, categories can perpetuate ingroup-outgroup boundaries, strengthening instead of solving discrimination or bias stemming from them (Ibid).

In fact, discrimination often goes hand and hand with categorisation and vice versa. For instance, in the case of direct discrimination, i.e., where machines "distinguish in a wrong way", any discrimination produced by them (through target variables or class labels) seldom gives rise to discriminatory dynamics of a traditional type openly targeting protected categories or social groups (Nardocci, 2021, p. 21). More often, it is an issue related to a *wrong association* among classes and characteristics, ultimately resulting in discrimination against specific categories. At the same time, in the case of indirect discrimination, as for the categories of anti-discrimination laws, establishing whether it is produced by machines is even

⁹ For instance, in the EU legal framework , *inter alia*, the Employment Equality Directive (2000/78/EC), the Racial Equality Directive (2000/43/EC), the Gender Goods and Services Directive (2004/113/ EC), the recast Gender Equality Directive (2006/54/EC).

more challenging. It occurs because they cannot fully replicate the complexity and heterogeneity of actual communities and their phenomenology in a virtual space (Ibid, p. 26). Since "models" are unable to reproduce (and predict) "relationships and proportions between categories in their actual density [...], proving a *disparate impact* becomes difficult if based on the real 'human' dimension and not on that assumed as a parameter by the machine, according to the data provided to it" (Ibid).

In this regard, data protection transparency can be better considered as "the beginning", an essential premise, rather than a goal, an end or the final achievement (Berendt, 2022, p. 19). It is no coincidence that the GDPR considers transparency as a fundamental principle in the processing of personal data (including sensitive data). However, as Berendt argues, data protection measures cannot be relied upon to mitigate *all* the negative (and discriminatory) effects produced by AI, especially in the case of cumulative impacts, where discrimination and bias may be considered as having "self-reinforcing" dynamics (cumulative causation) (Ibid, p. 14). Thus, "on a cultural and ideological level, the call for ever-expanding transparency of AI systems needs to be seen as an ideal as much as a form of 'truth production'" (Ferrer et al, 2021, p. 77).

As mentioned, even though final outputs are known, the process behind them is not, since the lack of transparency is inherent to AI (learning) processes (Casonato, 2019, p. 111).¹⁰ Hence, algorithmic discrimination may be difficult to tackle as compared to "traditional" discrimination since it appears "more abstract and unintuitive, subtle, intangible" (Simoncini, 2019, p. 92), and AI does not discriminate in the same way as humans (Ibid, p. 4).

2.3 Is the 'bias' approach enough?

Although bias is one of the recurrent causes and patterns of discrimination, it remains a separate concept. It holds a different ontological status.¹¹ Bias in itself can appear quite differently according to the context. Moreover, it can be detected in various stages of AI functioning and automatic decision-making processes. As a "deviation from the standard", bias can occur, for instance, in AI *modelling, training, or usage* (Ferrer et al., 2021, p. 72). Bias may arise from three main causes: firstly, it may be introduced 'on purpose' to correct pre-existing bias; second, it may be a result of pre-existing bias in the data set, where AI *learns* to replicate wrong past decisions¹²; thirdly, it may derive from de-contextualised usage of specific algorithms (transfer context bias), or algorithms whose output meaning is altered/distorted (interpretation bias) (Ibid).

A crucial point is "how much bias is too much" (Ferrer et al., 2021, p. 78). Since there are no absolute, general or standardised methods and parameters in this regard, there is no ideal

¹⁰ Put differently, we know that machines "give a certain answer, but we still don't know the *ratio*, or why [they] precisely provide *that* specific answer".

¹¹ "While the former (discrimination) may seem easy to define in terms of programmatic solutions, the latter involves a host of social and ethical issues that are challenging to resolve from a positivist framework", X. Ferrer, T. van Nuenen, J. M. Such, M. Côté, N. Criado, 2021. "Bias and Discrimination in AI: a cross-disciplinary perspective." *IEEE Technology and Society Magazine*, 40(2), p. 78.

¹² In this regard, the White Paper is well aware of this risk: "Bias and discrimination are inherent risks of any societal or economic activity. Human decision-making is not immune to mistakes and biases. However, the same bias when present in AI could have a much larger effect, affecting and discriminating many people without the social control mechanisms that govern human behaviour. This can also happen when the AI system 'learns' while in operation", p. 11.

approach.¹³ In this regard, a further crucial point refers to establishing "what counts as being equal", namely, which variables are relevant in what context, and based on what reasons (Hildebrandt, 2021, p. 365). From a legal perspective, bias also entails "the stereotype ready to turn into a discriminatory choice, and for this reason [it represents] the main target of the principle of non-discrimination" (Stradella, 2020, p. 2). In fact, if AI can fail like human intelligence, "it is also able to discriminate" (Ibid, p. 3). By reproducing structural discriminations of offline contexts in the online environment, bias can concretely foster forms of algorithmic *oppression* as well (Ibid, p.7).

As argued, identifying bias as the critical obstacle to establishing a genuinely equal (online) framework may not be enough or perhaps it can represent a partial response to discrimination. That is, it may be insufficient to consider a system *fair*, whether corrected or adjusted, just because it is free from bias (Stradella, 2020, p.6). Such a perspective still reflects the assumption of a neutral and objective nature of intelligent technologies, which can resolve asymmetries and structures of power relations, just as they are equally able to create them. The paradigm should shift to making "constitutional-oriented" algorithmic decisions, meaning algorithms that are also *aware* that they can discriminate (Ibid, p. 4).

From a reversed perspective, AI can help detect and tackle discrimination and inequality (Zuiderveen Borgesius, 2018, p. 18), since human decisions are also opaque (Heinrichs, 2022, p. 151). Thus, they can become a tool for technologically positive actions, considering bias as not *necessarily* generating unfair AI algorithms.¹⁴ This entails teaching AI to recognise bias-creating discrimination and learning to overcome stereotypes and prejudices. To investigate the possibility of AI as a tool for building a just and equal society, the issues to be addressed are not related to algorithms per se but broadly regard data, supervised learning, and their fair and correct construction as a "set" of information (Stradella, 2020, p. 2).

Another pivotal issue is at stake here: how much fairness is needed in order for AI to *act* free from bias? The main question concerns whether automatic or automated fairness is desirable and in the first place even if it is attainable. It has been argued not only that "fairness cannot and arguably should not be automated" (Wachter et al., 2021, p. 28) but also that it is not *computable* (Hildebrandt, 2021, p. 365). First, simply because there cannot be just a one-fits-all concept of fairness.¹⁵ Second, human cognition is still needed in order to tell what fairness *requires* in any case because "AI does not have a common sense understanding of contextual equality, cannot capture and consider local political, social and environmental factors" (Wachter et al., 2021, p. 20).

¹³ "Whether a biased decision can be considered discriminatory depends on many factors, such as the context in which AI is going to be deployed and the groups compared in the decision" X. Ferrer, T. van Nuenen, J. M. Such, M. Coté, N. Criado, 2021. "Bias and Discrimination in AI: a cross-disciplinary perspective." *IEEE Technology and Society Magazine*, 40(2), p. 78.

¹⁴ Precisely, it may be "necessary to think of AI and build algorithms as oriented *by default* to overcoming power asymmetries, and therefore, [...] biased to the extent that this serves to remove a rooted discrimination, or to neutralise an operating stereotype", E. Stradella, 2020. "Stereotipi e discriminazioni: dall'intelligenza umana all'intelligenza artificiale." *Costituzionalismo, Reti e Intelligenza Artificiale*, p.8.

¹⁵ As Berendt argued, indeed "different contexts and domains are perceived as requiring different notions of fairness and thus different metrics", pp. 15-16. As far as the impact this can bear on fundamental rights, the already mentioned FRA Report on AI and Fundamental rights states how: "There is a need for flexible impact assessments that can adapt to different situations given that fundamental rights violations are always contextual. [...] Fundamental rights compliance cannot be automated and hard-coded into computer software. Rather, each use case needs separate examination to determine whether any fundamental rights issue arises", p. 87.

3. AI, discrimination and (de)radicalisation

The concept of discrimination has been applied to underline how specific categories, groups and communities may suffer from discriminatory and unequal treatment by both "human" agents and machines. However, as mentioned, reality is much more complex and denser than the "abstract" environment machines can capture and *represent*. In this respect, it can be argued not only that "data-driven analytics create aggregates of individual profiles", but also that, as such, they are "prone to the production of arbitrary categories instead of real communities" (Ferrer et al., 2021, p. 76).¹⁶

In order to discuss these crucial points, we may propose a reversed approach towards bias and discrimination. The circumstance that categories and groups can be wrongfully represented means not only that a disadvantaged group may become a target of unfair treatment, but also that other groups or communities can remain invisible. In this case, the perspective on the minority is also in certain respects reversed: due to the significant attention focused on particular groups – in a discriminatory way – others can remain undetected, thus as if non-existent. This may happen because machines are trained in a biased way vis-à-vis racial, ethnic or religious minorities, which therefore become *over-represented*, and are "neutral" or "unconcerned" towards other communities, which end up being *under-represented*. For instance, the fact that AI perceives some specific neighbourhoods – where mostly people of colour live – as more dangerous can lead them to be more surveilled, regardless of the actual crime rates in that area. At the same time, a sort of AI "white blindness" may prevent the discovery of higher crime rates in places deemed 'safer', thus leading to a "faulty" prediction. This scheme can be replicated in many areas, such as the health and care sectors, finance (e.g. mortgages), employment (job applications), and so on.

In this report, categories are considered based on a reversed methodology, since over-representation is indicative of discrimination leading to the targeting of *those* groups or minorities. As D4 National Legal and Policies Reports have shown (D.Rad, 2022), most domestic counter-terrorism or counter-radicalisation legislation or policies have focused on jihadism (thus sometimes becoming biased against Muslim communities), and have underestimated alt-right and far-right movements, consequently failing to address the latter as a threat to public security. This may also occur in a virtual environment, especially in cyber security (Agarwal & Sureka, 2015; Vedaschi, 2020). Governments and public security forces can excessively concentrate their efforts on one kind of threat – perceived as more dangerous – and deliberately or unwittingly omit to address other threats. It can be an example of how a reversed-biased approach can be envisaged,¹⁷ also in the light of the concept of 'negative dominance', that is to say, the lack of representation, in a reversed way. Negative dominance entails that "minorities receive less protection just because they are minorities; therefore a certain group is "so small that none of them passes the legally required threshold" (Wachter

¹⁶ In fact, also, "Artificial" discrimination has transcended the notions of belonging and individual identity, redrawing the outlines of categories and groups" Nardocci, 2021, p. 59.

¹⁷ In this regard, see, for instance, Annex II to the 2020 FRA Report "Getting the future right. Artificial Intelligence and fundamental rights", which provides for "Examples of theoretical assessment of harm and significant impact of AI or automated decisions", taking into account "What happens if the output is wrong or if it works better in comparison with non-AI, human-based decisions?". In particular, as for 'predicting policing' examples of potential false positive and potential false negative are displayed. In the first case, the caused harm consists in the fact that "an innocent person is flagged to the police as a suspect"; in the second, that "A person engaged in criminal activity is not identified". Consequences can be several and diverse: *inter alia*, humiliation associated with discrimination or lack of trust in the public security", see https://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra_uploads/fra-2020-artificial-intelligence-annex-2_en.pdf.

et al., 2021, p. 28, 30). Accordingly, a certain kind of extremism might receive less attention precisely because it is under-detected and thus “invisible” from a legal point of view.

Moreover, due to the potential reflection of human bias, the machine may replicate that paradigm, and specific (extremist) groups, “not known in the virtual environment”, become as if non-existent (Nardocci, 2021, p.19).¹⁸ The reasons for this sort of reversed discrimination are varied. One explanation may precisely be the over-emphasis on specific kinds of extremisms perceived as more dangerous, also from a biased perspective (e.g. racism or xenophobia); another explanation might be that of the “major threat”: a result of the former. Secondly, a particular phenomenon may be deemed threatening for historical, social or political reasons; a third reason can be “neutrality”, i.e. a non-interventionist attitude towards some extremisms because of lack of concern or due to other priorities on the political agenda.

Another issue tied to radicalisation and technologies is the fuzzy lexicon: it is difficult to find a standardised parameter able to define all kinds of extremisms starting from the choice of keywords or “narratives”, as well as a general taxonomy encompassing different kind of radicalisation (Denaux and Gomez-Perez, 2019, p.3).¹⁹ Moreover, a comprehensive cross-disciplinary perspective would be required to tackle the issue. To say, to distinguishing between each context in the “identification of behavioural trends and radicalisation”.²⁰ In fact, a cross-disciplinary approach that takes account of legal, social, and ethical considerations has been suggested (Ferrer et al., 2021, p. 79), since technical knowledge on its own may result in reductionism if de-contextualised. Social and legal sciences, on the other hand, can provide solutions but are not equipped with technological tools to test their effectiveness.

Some studies about social media content broadly linked to “Islam” and “Muslim communities” show that the more or less “radical” attitude can change according to different topics, thus “potentially” violent discourse is spread on a *relative* basis instead of in *general* terms.²¹ Also, other additional challenges may arise and – bearing in mind the concept of “arbitrary” categories versus *real* communities and the difficulty of making some forms of extremism come to the (virtual) surface – one should be aware of the presence of a “vast subculture ecosystem in parallel to mainstream social media” (Crawford et al., 2021, p. 982).²²

A study conducted on chan sites – drawing alt- and far-right supporters or movements – showed that violence was not only trivialised in these contexts, but (also “key”) words and lexicon were not enough to detect violent extremist content. Their way of expressing ideas, content and messages was cultivated to be off-putting to newcomers – thus tricky to see for ‘outsiders’ or ‘uneducated’ users – and they also largely relied on *visual* means, thus “images [were] the most prolific in spreading hateful messages” (Ibid, p. 984). Additionally, most of

¹⁸ Even though the authors refer to reversed phenomena of discrimination against minorities, and here the expression is used in order to explain the concept of “invisibility” for and in the virtual space.

¹⁹ See also: Tanoli et al., 2021. Additionally, it has been underlined that “there are many tools to extract information from online sources, but there is a lack of a specific and specialised tool for online radicalisation, and this is a problem for Law Enforcement Agencies, Probation Services, Intelligence Services and also for researchers”, Camacho et al., 2016, p.4.

²⁰ In fact, in order “to successfully progress a profiling methodology utilising the analysis of data generated on social media, psychological and social models must also be utilised to correlate data with behaviours”, Chelvachandran and Jahankhani, 2019, p.1. See also: Almansoori et al., 2021, pp. 615-625.

²¹ See, e.g., Denaux & Gómez-Pérez (2019) who analysed different contents related to several topics – from discord between groups, to moral obligations, from the promotion of group ideology to the idealisation of the most radical members – with the aim of detecting changes in narratives. The authors examined different frameworks of communication: the “Young Muslim Digest”, the Al-Risalah of the Nusra Front, Dabiq, published by ISIS (2014-2016) and Rumiya, a magazine published by ISIS since 2016.

²² As has been observed: “To some, social media as a source of news and information sharing, is an alternative to what is what is deemed as the “censored, biased mainstream media”, Chelvachandran & Jahankhani, 2019, p.1.

them (not only “memes” in a technical sense) were images whose interpretation was challenging outside that subculture ecosystem. In most cases, they appeared *prima facie* inoffensive and naïve (Ibid, p. 986). These examples show how many challenges need to be confronted in the macro topic of AI and deradicalisation approaches.

4. (De)radicalisation and cyberspace: examples from Israel

This part describes trends of radicalization processes related to the virtual space (online) and connecting to the physical space (offline) and the state and civil modes of action that express attempts to apply deradicalization through prevention and interaction. The part focuses on the Israeli case, an environment that relies on advanced technologies in many security and civilian fields. The Israeli case study is brought here to discuss the boundaries between the need to use artificial intelligence technology to preserve human life and the need to protect human rights. The first segment will present radicalisation trends that connect the "online" space with the "offline" space. The second section will discuss state institutions' operation methods and the attitude towards the limits of using advanced technologies to prevent radicalization. The last part will present the civil society approach that emphasizes human and civil rights and takes interactive actions to lead deradicalization processes.

Cyberspace, as a metaphorical name for the Internet, is an inclusive set of systems that transfer information in which the World Wide Web is central (Hershkowitz et al., 2021, p. 14). Cyber defence/protection includes actions and responses designed to deal with threats to the integrity, safety and availability of computerised information. It does not refer to the hazards inherent in information content, such as expressions of hatred and slander, invasion of privacy, influence on elections, etc. Different types of cyber attacks become common – such as blocking access to healthcare systems or damaging state infrastructure – due to humanity's growing dependence on devices that connect to digital "central brains" (Ibid, p. 13). There is an increasing variety of motivations for cyber attacks, including goals of economic gain and of sowing destruction and fear as a means of terrorism, gathering of intelligence by states to achieve political and security benefits, and so on (Ibid, 58).

WP6 is oriented towards capturing critical moments affecting radicalisation by developing particular computational data science tools. "Toxicity" (or harmful usage) in social networks is a corollary of the growth in digital data made available through various social platforms in recent years. Toxic usage includes interruption of "normative" discourse (i.e. tolerance towards the other, non-violent appropriations, mutual respect of opinions, etc.) by publishing offensive and sometime violent videos and comments. In some cases, meetings among people give rise to harm; platforms like YouTube sometime supply fertile ground for toxic behaviour. During the COVID-19 pandemic, there was an increase in the dissemination of inciting content through social media, while harmful comments lead to more poisonous comments which reinforce each other (Obadimu, 2021). Scholars have tried to develop tools for analysing extreme views that might become part of radicalisation processes on social media platforms such as Twitter (Ajala et al. 2022).

In D6.1 we used machine learning to identify discourse that characterises an attraction to radical behaviour by forging a unique lexicon gathering together terms and themes indicative

of polarisation. Our model can potentially assist those providing support to people at Risk of Radicalisation (RoR) in real-time by enabling fast detection even of users with relatively little historical activity on social media sites (see D6.1). Following this assumption, in D6.2 we focused on the initiatives and actions undertaken by government organisations (GOs) and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) in relation to educational and social interactions within radicalisation set-ups (see D6.2). Based on this theoretical framework, we are exploring additional aspects to the future development of AI tools that might be useful in addressing (de)radicalisation and online/offline behaviour.

4.1 Online/Offline: traits of radicalisation

While working with stakeholders on the above issues, we have found a few specific topics that can shed some light on the characteristics of radicalisation within the offline/online space of investigation. The first one is the phenomenon of *incitement*. The hatred report published by BKC- the Berl Katznelson foundation in 2017 revealed that the number of racist, violent and offensive online comments within Israeli society was as high as 400,000 per month. Almost 3% had a clear call for violence (Berl Katznelson Centre, 2017). The year 2022 saw an overall decrease in violent internal speech but an increase in violent language against Russians in the context of the Russia-Ukraine war (BKC, 2022). Scholars call for laws and reinforced measures against incitement for racism offences committed through social media, among other things (Weschler-Beer et al. 2019, pp. 13-17), while understanding that radical online behaviour is no less offensive than offline behaviour, considering its viral effect.

An example of the effect of incitement can be taken from the events occurring in Israel during 11-14 May 2021, where Jewish and Arab civilians and residents of "mixed" cities²³ attacked each other brutally on the streets. For four days, citizens took the law into their own hands and acted in the place of the local and central governments (ITIC, 2021). It was revealed that arrangements and plans had been made before these events through social media, with inciting posts calling on Jews to retaliate against Arabs in the streets of mixed cities and vice versa (Peleg, 2022). The violence within these cities included Jewish terror attacks that were organised using social media, similarly to Palestinian nationalists' terror attacks. Consequently, when the street violence in the mixed cities was documented and spread across the cyberspace, online activity connected with the offline arena. The state attorney's request was to impose severe punishment on the perpetrators. The Supreme Court accepted the request, since the case involved an incitement to racism, which reflected a threat to democracy (Shimoni and Peleg, 2022). The Israeli State Comptroller's recent report criticised the authorities' failure to intervene and offer civilians protection, pointing to the grim outcome of the violence: three civilians killed, hundreds injured, and thousands arrested. It estimated that thousands of youths and young adults – 3200 Arabs and 240 Jews – participated in violent acts preceded by incitement on social media, which was among the factors leading to the clashes (State Comptroller, 2022). The criticisms also referred to the lack of intelligence and preliminary information regarding the intentions of those involved.

The above-described situation reflects a more profound challenge facing many states: the social media arena. Following the riots within the diverse cities, the Police Commissioner triggered a dispute when he suggested "shutting down access to social media platforms during extensive riots" (Haaretz editors, 2022). The Minister of National Defense (formerly known as

²³ Containing Jewish and Arab populations in shared living spaces (e.g., Aka, Lod, Beer Sheva, Bat Yam and more)

the Ministry of Internal Defence) objected to his suggestion, claiming that it was contrary to the values of a democratic regime (Walla editors, 2022). Some of the effects of a two-front battle – inside Israel and in the international arena – arouse increasing fear in the public due to the organised participation in violent acts. In addition, the acts have influenced worldwide public opinion, thus giving rise to antisemitic manifestations (Orpaz and Siman Tov, 2021). And so, the days of May 2021, in which violent riots occurred in the streets between Jews and Arabs, mainly showed the vivid connection between online incitement and offline violence.

The second phenomenon is the common usage of *fake news*. By definition, Fake news refers to "news content published on the Internet that aesthetically resembles legitimate mainstream news content, but that is fabricated or extremely inaccurate, also referred to as false, junk, or fabricated news" (Pennycook and Rand, 2021). Fake news is intended to mislead its consumers to the benefit of content-spread interests, sometimes oriented to emphasise an alternative claim, otherwise to attract attention away from the current one. The most notorious case that caused scholars and state actors to focus on this topic was the 2016 US elections, in which there were alleged attempts to influence the results by spreading lies as a tactic (Zhang and Ghorbani, 2020). In the above-mentioned case of the 2021 riots, the complex digital arena shared by Jews and Arabs included Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, Instagram and Telegram, with short inciting videos also posted on TikTok, which was central to the transmission of messages. The messages spread rapidly, increasing the phenomenon of fake news (Orpaz and Siman Tov, 2021, pp. 3-5), and were used for purposes of disinformation to sow public panic, resulting in an increase in the level of fear within the general population (Ibid, p. 7).

The third phenomenon that strengthens the voices of extremism on social media is the *copycat syndrome*. Social media is part of incitement mechanisms when an imminent threat comes from posts that might *inspire* other youngsters to commit violent acts. 'Copycatting' is a behaviour that usually emerges in times of conflict, where individuals or groups are encouraged to engage in actions similar to those committed by "lone wolves" (see D3.2). The phenomenon is not new, but it is amplified by social media's primary tool - publicity. The Israeli police said their worst fear came true when those who committed attacks during the riots inspired others to imitate their actions (Harel, 2022). The concern continues to grow as the IDF prepares for similar scenarios within the West Bank (Blumenthal et al., 2021).

Another form of inspiration for copycat actions that has developed recently manifests itself via "terror fashion", a new and popular mechanism that connects offline violent dress codes with online publications and purchases. T-shirts with a picture of an M-16 gun produced in Turkey spread across Arab villages and the Palestinian Authority jurisdiction, using violent images as an inspiration for mimicking extremism. In response, police have started enforcing measures against this "trend", claiming it is prohibited (Eli, 2022). The M-16 image is both a statement against Israel's military represented by its most common weapon type in use (M-16s) and a symbol of pro-Hamas struggle (Shapira, 2022; Cohen et al., 2022). The photos and physical appearance of kids, students and adults wearing T-Shirts depicting guns have caused rage within the Israeli public. Jewish separatist groups have printed their own T-shirts with the wording: "Death to Terrorists", used by far right-wing fanatics (Am Israel Chai, 2022) and distributed via social networks and websites. Again, social media is a central tool that allows radical ideas to reach their intended audience.

Another example from the "Pride Parades" in 2022 shows that social media can be a vehicle for the spread of radicalisation. Shortly before the pride parade of May 2022 in Jerusalem, a fake Facebook profile was created, featuring claims that the organisers would be subject to violent retribution should the parade take place (Chalabi, 2022). This statement was taken seriously by the authorities. In response, the state increased the number of security forces in the area. The speaker of the Israeli parliament said he was horrified by the copycat incitement, which mimicked previous violent events taking place in 2015 (see D3.2) (Hakmon and Bagano, 2022). In this case, local extremists were imitating death threats against the organisers (Yefet, 2022), showing how incidents of online inspiration using fake profiles and copycats of past violence can lead to actual actions offline.

4.2 State initiatives: cyberspace and security

The Internet has become a public forum for the expression of desires, aspirations, and opinions. It also connects to physical actions. It offers a variety of platforms that have become an instrument enabling state and civic actors to attract public attention. Social media networks such as Twitter, Facebook and YouTube serve as platforms for a broad exchange of ideas and opinions and are sometimes exploited by violent groups. The use of social media for radicalisation purposes has been the centre of attention of government agencies that handle security-related issues and seek to increase the levels of security by developing new technologies. Online radicalisation is confronted by adopting policies aimed at ensuring people's safety first of all, while not eliminating freedom of speech or privacy. Terrorist actors depend on the spread of information and rely on the Internet to disseminate their ideology, primarily through online social media applications (Greenberg, 2016, p. 165). For example, ISIS used the Internet to manipulate particularly younger people and make them embrace radical ideas, exploiting platforms such as Twitter and Facebook for their recruitment (Ibid, 166).

"Mind warfare" is one of the main motives underlying cyber attacks focused on influencing public opinion, distorting discussion, thus undermining personal security. Mind warfare is not limited to a war situation but also occurs regularly in other contexts. The dissemination of information through social networks is easy when content is uploaded and published without intermediaries, which makes spreading fake news a simple task. Mind warfare includes deleting, blocking, or copying information along with planting and distributing a lot of false information, for example, through social network posts, comments, internet articles and news articles from impersonating websites (Hershkovitz et al., 2021, p. 66). Most cyber attacks in this area are carried out using botnets ("digital bots"), simulating human users for attacks on state authorities; they are inspired by the desire to exact revenge or sow fear (Ibid, p. 67). Terrorist organisations try to influence the enemy's mind or motivate potential operatives to go out and commit terrorist acts. Civil society associations also use cognitive warfare to bring various issues to the public's attention (Ibid, p. 68).

Cyber defence requires considering both the need for protection and the right to privacy, even if it does not operate against every case of an attack. What emerges is a conflict of interest between privacy and cyber protection, reflecting the tension between freedom and security. The most prominent manifestation of this type of conflict is people's ability to use data and services in cyberspace anonymously. On the one hand, anonymous browsing means exercising the right to privacy, while on the other hand, it may contradict the goal of cyber

protection, which is to secure the cyberspace (Hershkovitz et al., 2021, p. 12). Due to the ability to obscure traces of Internet use, identifying actors is difficult (pp. 74-76).

Finding an entity accountable for cyber activity is complex and there is a debate as to whether responsibility lies with the owners of social platforms, private individuals or groups, or state actors. For example, in 2019, a US federal Court of Appeals (*Force v. Facebook, Inc.*, No. 18-397, 2d Cir., 2019) ruled that Facebook is not responsible for the publications of Hamas, designated as a terrorist organisation, and rejected the claim that the algorithms used automatically connect radical content and help spread it (Kahan, 2019). The authorities sometimes struggle to determine criminal liability for the distribution of offensive content on social media platforms (Unger, 2018, pp. 2-8). Article 25 (1-3) of the GDPR (European Union General Data Protection Regulations) requires that measures be taken to protect the private information of individuals (GDPR, 2016, directive 95/46/EC, chapter 4). A major issue is the ability to use services in cyberspace anonymously, because it is impossible to identify every internet user except in retrospect (Hershkovitz et al., 2021, 94-95). Cyber protection is an instrument and a precondition for ensuring the right to privacy. This aspect might reflect a necessity for possible computational models to address the issue.

Over the past few years, about 100 countries have adopted the American model for establishing national centres to manage "cyber incidents" which involve a violation of fundamental rights. These centres, referred to as Cyber Emergency Response Teams (CERT), were created for the purpose of transmitting information about cyber threats and attacks. After the UK joined the initiative in 2014 (CERT-UK), Israel started the CERT-IL in 2015 (Hershkovitz et al., 2021, 97-98), intending to address cyber incidents in the civilian cyber sphere. It receives and analyses hundreds of reports, including daily information from local and international partners regarding cyber attack attempts or threats. According to the CERT, its primary goal is to respond to cyber incidents by "promoting preventive activities, creating tailor-made partnerships and coordination between industries, government and international partners [...] enhancing information sharing, and preparing and issuing alerts to the public." (CERT-IL, 2022).

Considering that Israel sees itself as a 'cyber nation', the cyber security field is a central issue for Israeli developers (Unna, 2019, p. 167). Significant investments have been made in the cyber development industry, especially regarding security. As part of Israel's attempts to protect civil cyberspace, the INCD (Israel National Cyber Directorate) is "responsible for all aspects of cyber defence in the civilian sphere, from formulating policy and building technological power to operational defence in cyberspace". INCD provides incident-handling services and guidance for all civilian entities and critical infrastructures to increase the resilience of civilian cyberspace (INCD, 2022). Together with the police cyber unit established in 2012 (Maanit, 2012), the State Attorney Cyber Unit (SACU) has been working since 2015 to eliminate crime and terrorism in cyberspace using a punitive approach (SACU, 2021). It prosecutes digital offenders each year for incitement to terrorism, violence, publication of sexual content, etc. Its 2019 report showed that about 76% of removed content involved publications of terrorist organisations, and 22% dealt with incitement to violence and terrorism (SACU, 2020). There is also a new emergency hotline (105) for real-time reporting of online crimes against youths, set up by "The National Headquarters for the Protection of Children on the Internet" in 2018. Specialists from the Ministry of Health, Welfare and Social Affairs collaborate with the Justice Department and social workers in order to provide immediate

assistance to individuals under attack. Capturing the attackers prevents them from inspiring others (Ministry of Internal Defense, 2021).

Government organisations are well aware that in order to reach the public, they have to rely on technology and therefore be able to offer services and use cyberspace as a part of civic service tools (Bertot et al., 2010; Magro, 2012; Megdalia and Zheng, 2017). With respect to deradicalisation, state institutions have developed online reporting functions, in addition to those addressed to security authorities, whereby the public can submit reports to the relevant institution; this is slowly becoming a central practice. The fusion between the public's knowledge and state authorities' prevention mechanisms represents a prominent theme within the online/offline radicalisation framework. For example, in 2019, The ARCGU (Israel Anti-Racism Coordination Governmental Unit) prohibited racist comments on social media by public employees, encouraging the public to report such cases using the Internet. As a branch of the Justice Department, cooperating with the police, legislators, and public institutions, the ARCGU can recommend pressing charges against public institutions and employees accused of racist behaviour or offences that might lead to additional extremism. It also represents cases in court and supports individuals who have filed complaints (ARCGU, 2019). But sometimes, the information the government receives lacks valuable data that can only be found through non-governmental organisations (NGOs) having a more direct connection to various socio-cultural groups and individuals..

In 2019 a report from the Israeli Artificial Intelligence Committee (IAIC) addressed the dangers to human rights and economic competitiveness unjustly derived from automated AI functioning. It recommended the establishment of a new mechanism that would promote coordination of action among various authorities in this area. It focused on the need to "actively learn about the target populations that may be harmed due to technological developments based on artificial intelligence or be inadequately represented by the developers of the various systems" (IAIC, 2019). Its goal was to prevent biased technology from being implemented in the future development of AI tools.²⁴

Israel also joined the GPAI (Global partnership for Artificial Intelligence) in 2021 (Eichner 2021) and soon afterwards (2022) saw the launch of a "national AI plan", which aims to combine cyber solutions in the public sector. It attests to the government's desire to fulfil the country's image as a leader in AI technologies (INCD, 2022b). Moreover, the Israeli Ministry of Defence issued an updated statement regarding other states' options for requesting cyber security systems from Israel, conditioned on restricted usage (Form 8A, 2021). They are offered exclusively for the purpose of fighting against terrorism (Kobowitz, 2021). The document specifies that any such system can only be used to prevent and combat terrorist acts and serious crimes. As mentioned in section 2, "the system will be used only following national law, including legislation relating to privacy rights. [It] may be used only subject to obtaining any authorisation as required by national law, including judicial orders if so required." (Form 8A, 2021). In addition to obligating states to sign a legally binding agreement, the document emphasises the restrictions designed to prevent the misuse of cyber systems, including in matters related to human rights violations, as specified in section 3: "The system

²⁴ "[...] The report details a list of values that the committee seeks to protect, including: maintaining fairness, transparency, safety, freedom of choice, adherence to information security and human rights, including maintaining privacy, bodily integrity, civil and political rights, and maintaining personal autonomy. The committee also explicitly refers to the value of competitiveness and indicates the free market as a value that must also be guaranteed." (IAIC, 2019).

shall not be used, under any circumstances, to inflict harm on an individual or a group of individuals merely due to their religion, sex or gender, race, ethnic group, sexual orientation, nationality, country of origin, opinion, political affiliation, age or personal status." (Form 8A, 2021)

4.3 Civil society, cyberspace and human rights

NGOs are considered one of the pillars of democracies, a vital element of the civil society toolkit that meets essential needs in places where the government is out of reach, affecting the approach and practice of democracy in the global arena (Tallberg and Uhlin, 2011). NGOs play an essential part when it comes to the democratic regime. They help to express values of pluralism and liberty and shed light on civic issues that need attention. According to Lehr-Lehnardt (2005), the definition of an NGO is extensive. At its core, it is an organisation that is not part of the government, but is rather a part of the space between government and the private sphere/civic society. Its duties include promoting public interests, not for profit; it must engage in non-violent activity; it must be established by individuals, be independent and not supported by the state; and it must function with a minimal organisational structure (Lehr-Lehnardt, 2005, p. 3). The desire to influence government policy, locally, nationally and internationally, is common to all NGOs (Ibid, 4). In democracies, this sphere is large enough not to be "shut down" even during war or crises. Democracies partially depend on NGOs' initiative and joint interests to respond in real-time (Zaidise, 2008, p. 81).

Under non-democratic regimes, civil society has had a significant role in combating authoritarianism in Eastern Europe, the Middle East, China, South Africa and South America. Here we should note that not *all* civic activity emerges from this role, nor should it be assumed that all civil society organisations that claim to be NGOs have democratic values (Zaidise, 2008, 70-72). However, non-democratic regime leaders can exploit the very existence of NGOs in order to create a pretence of democratic values. For example, the uprising against the Mubarak regime in Egypt strengthened NGOs as legitimate actors. The social protest on 25 January 2011 emphasised that the third sector wished to take political advantage of the situation. Thus, human rights organisations initiated new projects aimed at constitutional reform, legal reform and transitional justice (Herrold, 2016, 189). The blossoming of NGOs began after the protest, consistently with the theoretical democratisation process, putting NGOs in the centre as a force of opposition to the government which acted in the name of citizens critical of the regime, and pursued collective interests (Ibid, 190-191). A vast third sector allows the government, among other things, to "project" liberal practices in front of international observers, since a developed civil society is a "sign" of democracy (Ibid). And so, NGOs' reputation as "serving democracy" was exploited by Egypt's government, as in the case above, when there was no coherent lawful attention to the need for independence and transparency.

Over the years, organisations have used social media to replace or supplement their official websites. The benefits include fast fundraising, transparency and accountability, operational involvement and engagement, and image improvement (Di Lauro et al., 2019, 1-2). "Cyber volunteering" (or "online volunteering") is a common phenomenon that has emerged alongside technological progress. New media tools have significantly increased NGOs' ability to communicate with their clients. Accordingly, they are using social media to reach more desirable groups and individuals. Many are active on Facebook, Twitter and Instagram as they

seek to promote their mission and share information about their activity (Raja-Yosuf et al., 2016, p. 388). Their activities include training, fundraising, information sharing and problem solving, geared towards the fulfilment of NGOs' social tasks (Ibid, 395). Online tools have made the connection between the third sector and the public more robust (Sheombar et al., 2018), so using digital tools saves costs for NGOs with limited resources (Raja-Yosuf, 2016, p. 395).

Since 2016, the government has been implementing legislative measures to supervise violence on social media. In 2018 it attempted to promote a new statute regarding social media Incitement Prevention.²⁵ The bill, also named the "Facebook Law", wishes to authorise State Attorney's Office to request a district court judge to order to remove content posted online (Altshuler, 2022; Knesset, 2018). Though it has not yet been enacted, some say that the law, in its current version, puts freedom of speech in jeopardy and is too restrictive, since it addresses all websites and not just social media (Haaretz, 2021). Those who oppose it claim that such a law might lead to unlimited power of censorship in the hands of the state, which puts *human rights at risk* in the long run. Politicians want to allow this law to pass, but it seems that it restricts them as well; hence, it has not yet found a way into the Israeli Book of Laws.

In Israel, the strengthening of NGOs may partly be explained by the fact that most Israeli citizens do not have high trust in political parties and organisations (Yishai, 2012). Some NGOs are used as a "political supplement", while others take over the government's role in supplying goods when the authorities cannot meet humanitarian needs (Ibid, 290-295). NGOs can connect people and government, but they are simultaneously separate, since they are more exposed to events on the ground level. The third sector has become more vigorous in the past decade in parallel to civic activity aimed at achieving a democratic regime. Some NGOs turn to active judicial procedures when the state does not respond adequately. In a petition submitted in 2018 by the "Adalah Center", it was claimed that the national cyber unit has an "arbitrary enforcement" mechanism that severely violates the freedom of expression and due process, hence does not meet the conditions of the "limitation clause" in respect of human rights laws.²⁶ The movement for "Freedom of Information", asked to join the petition as a friend of the court, emphasised the lack of transparency in the cyber unit's activities (Adalah 2021). The Supreme Court (No. 7846-19) rejected the petition, ruling that the cyber division of the government could continue to ask social media platforms to remove certain content of specific users in cases of incitement and the dissemination of notions that are against Israeli law (Kabir, 2021). To conclude, it is essential to emphasise that cooperation between the cyber security state officials' protection efforts of and NGO activities regarding human rights can give rise to vast data banks. These can assist in pinpointing cases of legal violations and threats within social media. Legislation must be consistent with the pre-eminent issues (i.e., the I-GAP spectrum) related to acts of radicalisation that are recognised by NGOs, sometimes faster than the state, due to their expansion to social media platforms. Following the previous sections, here it needs to be considered that AI can serve both as a tool that unconsciously "progresses" discriminatory acts (see section 3) and as a framework for

²⁵ The full name of the law: "A bill to prevent the commission of offenses through internet advertising (removal of content)-2018", last submitted on 7 July 2018, current status: ready for second and third parliamentary vote.

²⁶ A Limitation Clause, found in certain current Basic Laws (i.e., Freedom of employment, and Human Dignity and Liberty) allows the Knesset to pass ordinary legislation contradicting constitutional legislation, so long as certain procedural and/or substantive conditions are fulfilled (Knesset, 2023); Article 8 of "Basic law: human dignity and freedom" suggests that "'One is not to violate the rights accorded by this Basic Law save by means of a law that corresponds to the values of the State of Israel, which serves an appropriate purpose, and to an extent that does not exceed what is required, or on the basis of a law, as aforementioned, by force of an explicit authorization therein."

eliminating such actions by utilising big data serving human rights as a starting point. AI usage by the state or NGOs is supposed to comply with anti-discriminatory algorithms to fulfill human rights orientation. This object has become central in the current period due to the increased awareness of the lack of and the need for a legislative and regulatory framework concerning the development and usage of artificial intelligence.

5. Conclusive remarks

As the above review has shown, AI and machine learning will increasingly become inherent in all human activities, actions and operations. Notwithstanding the challenges it poses to the ordinary perception of 'cognitive' processes, AI remains a valuable support in different fields of knowledge. Perhaps its scope, purposes and helpfulness will be increased in the future. We will also *learn* to deal with its harmful (or threatening) outcomes. That is, AI is not dangerous in itself, but the multifarious ways through which it can be used might show shortcomings, especially whether sensitive data are exploited.²⁷

Those seeking to address radicalisation-related issues encounter major challenges regarding reverse discrimination towards certain groups or political ideologies due to an over-emphasis and an overestimation of other types of extremism. The latter can also stem from a biased approach and discriminatory treatment against specific violent behaviours because they have been deemed a priority for national security or public order, *among other things*. In this regard, two main recommendations can be offered. First, as suggested by scholars who have focused on this topic, bias can be fruitfully applied in a reversed way, i.e., to let AI "know" where it mistreats, mismatches or discriminates. To make it recognise its own bias or teach it *what* discrimination *means* and *which* forms of discrimination are concerned in order that they may be discovered and overcome. Furthermore, mitigating asymmetries is also a matter of "distributive justice". Accordingly, the following question arises: can distributive justice be used as a basis for introducing "fair design" in machine learning systems, as an act of fairness?²⁸ (Hildebrandt, 2021, p.358).²⁹ It is possible to accomplish the same thing through algorithms that resolve inequalities. In this regard, the I-GAP spectrum and its features would also be dramatically impacted; grievances and Alienation develop from a sense of exclusion and discrimination, while polarisation may well represent one of the consequences of a (perceived) unjust, 'unfair' and unequal society.

Secondly, AI should be made subject to ad-hoc regulation in the field of radicalisation since, as several studies have proved, issues arise when it comes to confronting different narratives, behavioural models or, more simply, "keywords" (or images) whenever crucial in a radicalisation process. Moreover, regulating AI in a general, out-of-context (and off-topic) way

²⁷ As effectively addressed in the White Paper, in fact: "While AI can do much good, including by making products and processes safer, it can also do harm. This harm might be both material (safety and health of individuals, including loss of life, damage to property) and immaterial (loss of privacy, limitations to the right of freedom of expression, human dignity, discrimination for instance in access to employment), and can relate to a wide variety of risks. A regulatory framework should concentrate on how to minimise the various risks of potential harm, in particular the most significant ones. The main risks related to the use of AI concern the application of rules designed to protect fundamental rights (including personal data and privacy protection and non-discrimination), as well as safety and liability-related issues", p. 10.

²⁸ "Can we design automated decision-making (ADM) and automated decision support (ADS) systems such that they avoid both direct and indirect exclusion from what people deserve, desire or need?" (Ibid, p. 364)

²⁹ "It is about similar cases being treated similarly to the extent of their similarity. This raises questions about which cases are similar and what factors are relevant to decide on similarity and thereby on difference. People are of course never entirely similar, so we need to know what difference counts and which difference should not be taken into account when governments decide on policies that affects their citizens and when they actually decide individual cases."

will not provide successful solutions.³⁰ AI blindness to specific circumstances or changing, dynamic (personal, social, economic, political) situations does not *automatically* imply its neutrality or fairness. On the contrary, it might not only replicate “offline” stereotypes, prejudices and under-reporting, but could also enhance and exacerbate them. Data protection or algorithmic ‘transparency’ is not enough on its own, nor does it represent *the* solution to all AI-related issues. Human intelligence, along with human ethics and values, should preserve its crucial role of guiding and supervising machines’ activities and their improvement, since “[...] this also distinguishes discernment from calculation and computation [...]” – practices that involve mathematics of numbers and do not possess ethical values – “Whereas we do not expect plants or elephants to give reasons for how they discriminate, we do expect awareness and reflection from human persons.” (Hildebrandt, 2021, p.360, 365)

In the previous report (D6.2), we showed two central pathways for deradicalisation—preventive and integrative. When it comes to detecting radicalisation, both are based on information that the public submits to the relevant institution (GO/NGO). As a prominent player in the exploration of the online/offline radicalisation framework, NGOs can capture events sometimes faster than the security authorities, since they gather much more data than GOs, using more advanced technology, such as computerised data-collecting tools on social media. Yet both need assistance in handling, transferring and accumulating Big Data, an essential task AI algorithm design could solve, for example, by developing an automated analysis and report creators. Here is where a fairer approach is required: when creating a linguistic framework for detecting users at Risk of Radicalisation (RoR), it is necessary to rely on data emerging both from GOs and NGOs, configuring that the preliminary research and modifications of designed systems should be oriented to eliminate discriminatory and biased tendencies among developers.

The knowledge of NGOs can be valuable to the state for the purpose of developing deradicalisation initiatives. AI technologies can produce analytical data reports for tracking occurrences within "backlash" populations – minorities who suffer from broad exclusion due to institutionalised discrimination. But when an NGO lacks a vast presence within social media, the knowledge it possesses mainly stays within the organisation. Social media publications that offer a safe space for reporting human rights violations can help NGO to recruit more volunteers and raise public awareness about radicalisation processes. Informing about any harm done might contribute to reducing violent online discourse while empowering field experts in offline deradicalisation organisations. The latter must have a more direct approach to state institutions in order to provide them with valuable information regarding radical, discriminatory or biased acts so that they may adjust their AI systems accordingly.

Finally, applying AI systems in the attempt to support deradicalisation processes requires combining manual and digital work, hence the fusion of existing interdisciplinary knowledge with new technological tools. Given the growing usage of social media platforms as both a separating and socialising space, addressing this matter requires adjusting legal principles and applying social science sensitivities within new AI designs. Adapting AI tools to advance fundamental human rights might help to prevent the transformation of radicalisation from

³⁰ For instance, “Additional regulation should be considered, because AI decision-making that escapes non-discrimination law can still be unfair. But it is probably not useful to adopt rules for AI decision-making in general. AI is used in many different sectors and for many purposes, and often, AI does not threaten human rights. [...] But regulating AI in general is not the right approach, as the use of AI systems is too varied for one set of rules. We need sector-specific rules, because different values are at stake, and different problems arise, in different sectors” (Zuiderveen Borgesius, 2018, pp. 38, 40).

online space to offline practice. Eliminating fundamentally unjust discrimination directed against communities and individuals that endure racist responses serves as a pacifying act for future online users. It might reduce the chances of developing a sense of *Injustice*, *Grievance*, continuing with *Alienation* and *Polarisation*.

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